

Skills 4 eosc

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Milestone Abstract

This short report reflects the experience of the pilot training in Open Science for PhD candidates held at the UC3M-Skills4EOSC partner in March-June 2024. The course gathers the OS Essentials course for PhD students: "UC3M Ticket to Open Science" inspired by the document "*Passport for Open Science: A practical guide for PhD students*" was designed and performed by the Skills4EOSC project, WP4, T4.4.

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TERMINOLOGY

<https://eosc-portal.eu/glossary>

<i>Acronym</i>	<i>Definition</i>
ECR	Early Career Researchers
EOSC	European Open Science Cloud
ERA	European Research Area
FAIR	Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable
HE	Higher Education
HEI	Higher Education Institutions
MVS	Minimum Viable Skillset
OS	Open Science
OSE	Open Science Essentials
RRA	Responsible Research Assessment
TtT	Train the Trainers
UC3M	Universidad Carlos III de Madrid
UC3MT2OS	UC3M Ticket to Open Science

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1 Executive summary

As part of Task 4.4 of the Skills4EOSC project, Universidad Carlos III de Madrid (UC3M) designed and piloted the course “Ticket to Open Science” (UC3MT2OS), a modular training programme for PhD candidates aimed at developing essential Open Science (OS) skills aligned with the Minimum Viable Skillset (MVS) and the FAIR-by-design methodology.

The pilot built upon a mapping of existing OS training programs across Europe, identifying both good practices and gaps—particularly in the areas of reproducibility, citizen science, and research assessment reform. Drawing inspiration from UC3M’s previous "Ticket2OS" course and international references such as DIOSI. The pilot delivered a comprehensive 30-hour online course in English, integrating 10 core modules, weekly sessions, OS cafés, and a micro-credentialing system based on learner engagement and competencies.

A total of 19 doctoral candidates participated, with 13 completing final public reflections that demonstrated transformative effects on their research attitudes and practices, especially in areas such as FAIR data, data sharing, ethical-legal aspects, and open publishing. The course fostered a community-oriented learning approach and provided a scalable model for OS capacity-building in doctoral education. Key recommendations include reinforcing post-course feedback mechanisms and enhancing alignment with badge-based micro-credentialing.

Sessions lasted from March to May 2024 and were supported by practical exercises, discussions, and reflective assignments. The program aimed to empower PhD candidates with a foundational understanding and hands-on application of OS principles, equipping them with tools to act as informed advocates of open, FAIR-aligned research practices within their disciplines.

2 OS Essentials for PhD candidates' design process

In this section, we will briefly introduce the design process of the OS Essentials for PhD candidates (this methodology will be covered in more detail in the final deliverable D4.3 Open Science Essentials for undergraduate programmes and Doctoral Schools, from Task 4.4 and Task 4.3).

2.1 Mapping of already existing training

A mapping exercise was conducted on existing training programs within and beyond the Skills4EOSC consortium. This landscaping work helped to identify best practices and fill content gaps as well as to guarantee the analysis of the varied profile of the target audience, within national contexts and fields.

Among the internal references, particular attention was given to:

- [UC3M Ticket2OS course](#), which had been previously offered to doctoral students at Carlos III University of Madrid, forming the baseline model of the pilot.
- Training in OS for PhD candidates from Skills4EOSC partner institutions, which provided targeted modules on Open Access, FAIR principles, and ethical and legal considerations. These partner institutions included:
 - Karolinska Institute - [Open Science and Reproducible Research course](#)
 - DKB - [Open up your Academic Publishing Toolbox](#)
 - TU Wien - [Scientific work: Publishing and Dissemination](#)
 - SDU - [Responsible Conduct of Research](#) (Module 3: Research data management)
 - TU Delft - [Open Science: Sharing your research with the world](#)
 - KIT - [RDMToolKIT](#)
 - POLITO - [Research Data Management and Open Science](#)
 - CBS - [Introduction to Research Data Management for PhD Students](#)
 - TAU - [TAU Library Guide: Research Data Management](#)

Externally, several influential programs and resources were reviewed:

- The [DIOSI Project](#) series of Train-the-Trainer courses: TtT - Open Science & Open Access Publishing, TtT - FAIR Research Data Management and TtT - Open Innovation & Entrepreneurship (OI&E). From the latter TtT, we included

in our pilot one-hour session *OS Café* (on Module 5) to explore Open Innovation and Entrepreneurship.

- The [ERUA Open Science Fundamental Course](#) (European Reform University Alliance).
- [Re-UNITA project's trainings](#) on Open Science for PhDs.

The mapping process identified several key findings:

- Open Access and FAIR principles were nearly universal in training content, but implementations varied in depth and pedagogical design.
- Topics such as citizen science, Responsible Research Assessment (RRA), and pre-registration were less frequently covered, indicating areas where the pilot could add unique value.
- Many programs lacked a clear articulated competency framework or link to micro-credential systems, highlighting the innovation in the pilot's alignment with the Minimum Viable Skillset (MVS) and its tiered certification approach.
- Tools training (e.g., Zenodo, Argos, RMarkdown) was often delivered inconsistently, which led to the UC3M Ticket to OS pilot to explicitly integrate these into a module with hands-on activities.

2.2 UC3M Ticket to Open Science previous program

The previous course of the UC3M Ticket to Open Science (2022) was used as a baseline program for the pilot in terms of content and structure, including modules on Open Access publishing, data management, FAIR principles, and responsible research. The original course originated as an adaptation/inspiration of the French document of [The Passport for Open Science - A Practical Guide for PhD Students](#), continuing with the journey metaphor to Open Science (Passport, ticket and also frequent flyer cards as badges).

We also reused the practice of introducing a one-hour session of *OS Café* after each module to delve into specific topics of interest for the target audience in a local context. *OS Cafés* are online webinars that combine discussions with training workshops. These Open Science Cafés are meant to be open to all teaching and research staff and interested researchers (including senior and PhD advisors), as well as doctoral students. Thus, in the OS Cafés we open the opportunity to build a broader and richer community for the PhD students joining the course.

3 PILOT: UC3M Ticket 2 Open Science 2024

3.1. A brief description of the pilot

The pilot training “UC3M Ticket to Open Science” (Ticket2OS) was conducted in English and, throughout 30 hours of online instruction, it combined weekly sessions, Open Science cafés, and the possibility to acquire micro-credentials. To earn 3 ECTS, students were required to maintain 80% attendance, actively engage in course activities, and produce a final public post reflecting on their learning journey and performance during the course.

The curriculum covered 10 key modules, including –among other topics– Open Access, FAIR data, citizen science, research assessment reform, reproducibility, and ethical-legal issues.

Table 1. Pilot’s course learning objectives

UC3M Ticket2OS course learning objectives

Understanding Open Science (OS) Fundamentals. Gain a comprehensive understanding of Open Science concepts, policies and challenges.

Developing a personal Open Science Strategy for your research during your PhD and beyond, covering aspects like thesis, publications, data sharing, reproducibility... and overall research approach.

Hands-on experience with Open Science Tools. Familiarize participants with practical tools and resources for OS, encouraging collaborative research.

Understanding the importance and various aspects of Open Access publishing, including different routes, versions of papers, and the role of repositories.

Understanding and applying FAIR data principles, create Data Management Plans (DMP) and explore data repositories.

Learning strategies for improving reproducibility in research, understand the concept of pre-registration, and apply them in practical exercises.

Exploring the principles, types, and platforms of Citizen Science, and engage in practical activities related to citizen science projects.

Grasp the ethical, legal and social issues (ELSI) of Open Science, including IPR, copyrights, privacy, and responsible research practices.

Understanding the need for reform in Research Assessment, analysing the main current initiatives (CoARA) and learn to create narrative CV.

Learning and using the support provided by UC3M through the Unit for Open Science (UnIOS).

Create an Open Science community at UC3M.

3.2. Program, Trainers, dates and duration

Ticket2OS UC3M course				
Num	Trainer	Dates	Proposed Modules	Topics
1	Eva Méndez and Pablo Sánchez Núñez	13 March (12:00-14:00)	Ethos and Introduction to Open Science	<p>Introduction about the course. Learning outcomes and evaluation</p> <p>You & Open Science: a new paradigm for your research (icebreaking)</p> <p>What is Open Science (Open Science, Open Knowledge, Open Research, Open Scholarship)</p> <p>Why Open Science and How to make it happen. Benefits of Open Science for researchers and society.</p> <p>Open Science components and Challenges</p> <p>Current Researchers 35 times Open: The European Competence Framework for Researchers (CFR. 2022)</p> <p>Evolution and current policies for Open Science (declarations, initiatives and the rules of the game):</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Main actions, documents and policies in Europe and world-wide (UNESCO Recommendation) to promote and implement Open Science. - Open Science in the Spanish Research Landscape (Spanish Legislation on Science and Universities, Doctoral rules and practices RD 99/2011, Spanish Strategy on Open Science (ENCA2023).
2	Eva Méndez and Pablo Sánchez Núñez	20 March (12:00-14:00)	Planning your responsible research in the Open	<p>How to become an Open Responsible Scientist</p> <p>Including Open Science Practices in the whole research Cycle.</p> <p>Open Science Tools and collaborative research. (101Tools-Utrecht and DOST (Digital Open Science Tools): Reference management and discovery tools; Tools for analysis; Collaborative writing platforms; other tools to produce content; Annotation and review tools; Tools for your research outreach.</p> <p>Planning YOUR STRATEGY to Open Science: You, Your thesis, Your publications, Your data (sharing), your other research outcomes</p> <p>EDI: Equity, Diversity and Inclusion principles and standards</p> <p>Initiatives and resources for Early Career Researchers and PhD candidates to practice Open Science:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Learning resources: Open Science Passport, Open Science MOOC, etc. - Communities: MC association, EURODOC, RDA, etc. - Open Science @uc3m: you are part of our journey. Building OS Communities. Slack channel.
		15:00-16:00		<p>OS Café: Open Science: lessons and help from OpenAire. Giulia Malaguarnera. OpenAIRE Outreach and Engagement Officer. Ex-president of EURODOC.</p>
3	Gema Bueno de la Fuente	3 April (12:00-14:00)	Disseminating your research: Open access publications	<p>What is open access publishing?</p> <p>OA history and declarations: +20 years of OA</p> <p>Benefits and challenges of OA publishing.</p> <p>Open Access routes: gold, green, diamond, etc.</p> <p>PlanS & cOAlitionS, transformative agreements and current trends (Rights Retention Strategy (RRS).</p> <p>Versions of your paper: version of the author (preprint/post print), VoR, etc. and how to know the right version to share (Sherpa/Romeo)</p> <p>Preprints and Open Peer Review</p> <p>Repositories: types and use.</p> <p>Social networks for scientists. Repositories vs. Social Scientific Networks (ex. ResearchGate)</p> <p>Predatory publishers/journals: How to identify them</p> <p>How to choose an Open Science Journal? criteria, resources and practical guidance</p>
		(15:00 - 16:00)		<p>OS Café: Open Science in the new ERA (European Research Area) and Horizon Europe. Javier López Albacete. Policy Officer. Open Science and Research Infrastructures. DG Research & Innovation. EU Commission.</p>

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4	Sara Martínez Cardama	10 April (12:00-14:00)	Disseminating your research data: Open and FAIR data	What is Open Data, Open Research Data and FAIR data.
		(15:00 - 16:00)		<p>Types of row data (qualitative and quantitative).</p> <p>FAIR data principles: Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Reusable.</p> <p>CARE principles (Collective benefit, Authority to Control, Responsibility and Ethics).</p> <p>Metadata and PIDs.</p> <p>Data Management Plans (DMP) and outcome management plans.</p> <p>How to create a DMP: Tools and standards.</p> <p>Regulation around data/open data, further than research data: GDPR, EU directive on Open Data (1024/2019)</p> <p>The principle "as open as possible, as closed as necessary"</p> <p>Licensing FAIR data for Reuse (see. ELSI session)</p> <p>Current Data repositories and EOSC. Search for RD repositories (re3data). Tools (OSF), and other infrastructures.</p> <p>OS Café: Create your Data Management Plan and make your data FAIR. Joy Davidson. Associate Director. Digital Curation Centre. FAIRImpact EU funded project.</p>
5	Raúl Aguilera	17 April (12:00-14:00)	How UC3M will help you to be an Open Scientist: UniOS & Library support	Authorship and affiliation
		(15:00 - 16:00)		<p>Persistent Identifier for researchers: ORCID uses at UC3M</p> <p>Your thesis step by step: a library guide to help you with your thesis</p> <p>How to publish in Open Access your thesis and your publications:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The Institutional Repository e-Archivo. - Your thesis in Open Access (embargoes and exceptions) <p>Open Science and the dissemination of research outcomes. Regional Research Portal: InvestigaM (Consortio Madroño):</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - How to create a data management plan for your thesis - Regional Repository: e-Ciencia - Data Management and Regional Data Repository: e-CienciaDatos: a place for your thesis's data <p>Blog I+B: Investigación y Biblioteca (R+L: Research and Library)</p> <p>Where we are and how to make it happen:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Open Science support (UniOS) - Full Open Science Pilot (FOS). <p>OS Café: Open Innovation and Entrepreneurship. Marco Masia. Head of Entrepreneurship. University of Vienna.</p>
6	Pablo Sánchez Núñez and Iñaki Ucar Marqués	24 April (12:00-14:00)	Pre-registration and Reproducibility	<p>Reusability, Replication, and Reproducibility (RRR):</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The role of reproducibility in Scientific research. Reproducibility crisis and National Reproducibility Networks. - Challenges in reproducibility: publication bias, QRP (Questionable Research, Practices, etc.) - Strategies and best practices on improving reproducibility. - Create a reproducible data analysis using knitr. - Tools for improving reproducibility: RMarkdown, Jupyter notebook, etc. <p>Concept of preregistration and disciplines that practice pre-registration:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Design a pre-registered study. - Pre-registration platforms and templates: Aspredicted, OSF, etc.
7	Luca Schirru	8 May (12:00-14:00)	Ethical, Legal and Social Issues (ELSI) of Open Science	Legal issues in research outputs:
		(15:00 - 16:00)		<p>Ethics in Open Science:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - General Ethical Principles, Frameworks (e.g. RRI: Responsible Research and Innovation) and Codes (e.g. the European Code of Conduct for Research Integrity) applicable to Research in the EU - Best practices in Open Research <p>OS Café: Navigating the intersection of IPR and Open Science. Dr. Javier de la Cueva. Lawyer and Researcher. Author of https://openscience-ipr.eu</p>
8	Eva Méndez	15 May (12:00-14:00)	Citizen Science and public engagement	What is citizen science. History and evolution of CS.
		(15:00 - 16:00)		<p>Citizen Science and public engagement: difference and confluence.</p> <p>Citizen science principles (10) and characteristics.</p> <p>Types of citizen science projects.</p> <p>CS platforms and communities (CitizenScience toolkit, SciStarter, national CS platforms and communities).</p> <p>Create your own project of CS.</p> <p>CS in educational settings: Open Educational Resources and citizen science</p> <p>Other approaches to citizen science: CERI (Community Engagement Responsible Research and Innovation), YUFE approach to CS within YUFERING project.</p> <p>Citizen Science successful use cases at UC3M:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - LADA-UC3M: citizen science in urban archaeology research. Jesús Bermejo. Humanities: History, Geography and Art Department - Mental Health research and citizen science. Anxo Sánchez. Complex Systems Interdisciplinary Group (GISC). Mathematics Department. <p>OS Café: Citizen Science. Endless possibilities for a Healthier and sustainable society. Fermín Serrano. IberCivis foundation. Spanish observatory for Citizen Science.</p>

9	Eva Méndez	22 May (12:00-14:00)	RRA Responsible Research Assessment: Towards a reform of the Research Evaluation	Traditional Research Assessment methods and practices: the biggest barrier for Open Science.
		(15:00 - 16:00)		Principles of Responsible Research Assessment (RRA). Benefits of Implementing RRA in Research Evaluation. Challenges to Reforming Research Assessment. Current movements and initiatives to Reform Research Assessment world-wide: DORA Declaration, Leiden Manifesto, The Metric Tide, CoARA, etc. CoARA: an opportunity to change research evaluation. CoARA Working Groups and National Chapters. Case Studies of Successful Implementation of RRA. Tools and Resources for Implementing RRA: Next Generation Metrics and CAM (Career Assessment Matrix). Open bibliographic data (open metadata). EMCR and Research Assessment. OS Café: Responsible Research Assessment and Open infrastructures for research evaluation. Dr. Cameron Neylon. COKI (Curtin Open Knowledge Initiative). Professor of Research Communications. Curtin University, Perth, WA.
10	Eva Méndez and Sebastian Dahle	22 May (12:00-14:00)	Discipline-oriented Open Science	Doctoral candidates will make groups by discipline/area (e. g. Social Sciences, Humanities, Engineering, Law, etc.) and contact the University Unit on Open Science (UniOS) to have a special session focusing on the OS issues in their discipline. To organize yourselves by groups, you might use the Forum in AG or contact students from the same discipline/same interests through the Slack Community Channel.
FINAL Assignment / practice 10: All the students, aiming to complete the course and obtaining the 3ECTS must write, and openly share, a final post about the content of the course and his/her learning and performance during the course. All the posts have to be published in the website before June, 5th.				

3.3. Micro-credentials

Participants were eligible to earn micro-credentials based on their engagement and demonstrated competencies. Continuing with the aeroplane journey metaphor, we used the flying membership categories/cards used by some airlines, and based on experience points to correlate with different levels of competencies:

- **Open Science Silver:** completed modules 1, 2 and 3
- **Open Science Gold:** completed modules 1, 2, 3, 4, 5 and 6
- **Open Science Platinum:** completed modules 1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6, 7, 8, 9 and 10
- **Open Science Platinum (Singular):** completed modules 1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6, 7, 8, 9, 10 and Final Assignment

These micro-credentials provided a structured pathway for learners to gain recognition for acquiring OS skills in a flexible, modular format.

3.4 Alignment with the MVS and the FAIR-by-design methodology

The pilot training program was aligned by module with the [MVS profile for ECRs](#), covering essential competencies and soft skills expected from PhD candidates engaged in Open Science. **Key competency areas addressed:**

- Understanding of Open Science practices
- Application of FAIR principles to research outputs

- Knowledge of research data life cycles
- Awareness of open access publishing, repositories, and open peer review
- Digital skills related to open data and research workflows

Soft skills developed:

- Ethical orientation toward OS
- Collaboration and time management
- Adaptability and public engagement

In addition, this alignment was complemented with the FAIR-by-design methodology. Each module introduces a set of learning objectives that are correlated with the content covered in that module, the competences and skills trained (MVS) and the activity that closes each session.

In the [Appendix](#) of this report, we explain in detail the alignment of the pilot's program, learning objectives and activities with the corresponding MVS profile's skills and competences (MVS profile for Early Career Researcher) and the FAIR-by-design methodology.

3.5 Results and feedback

A total of 19 PhD candidates from diverse academic disciplines at Carlos III University of Madrid participated in the pilot course. Of these, 13 submitted reflective final contributions evaluating the course's impact and their personal journey through Open Science (visit the [blog](#) section in the course website to read students' posts on this regard).

The 13 students providing feedback represented a broad range of disciplines, including law, library and information science, computer science, engineering, biomedical science, and media research. These posts served as qualitative indicators of the course's effectiveness and highlighted the personal and professional transformations prompted by the training.

These submissions revealed transformative changes in their research practices and attitudes toward Open Science. Learners reported:

- **Improved technical skills**, especially in applying FAIR principles, creating Data Management Plans, and using tools such as RMarkdown and ARGOS.

- **Data management and accessibility:** Students emphasized how the course improved their ability to access, share, and manage research outputs using open tools like Zenodo, GitHub, and OpenAIRE.
- **Ethical and philosophical shifts:** many participants expressed a deepened philosophical commitment to openness, often linking the course to broader values like equity, collaboration, and transparency. The Ethical, Legal, and Social Issues (ELSI) module was highlighted as particularly impactful.
- **Cultural transformation in scientific research:** many students highlighted the need for open science, despite being aware of the prevailing research culture, like current evaluation metrics.

5 Lessons learned and recommendations

The 2024 UC3M Ticket to Open Science course is a scalable training model that reflects European OS priorities while offering practical, pedagogical, and credential-based value for PhD candidates, aligned with the competences and skills of the MVS profile for ECR.

However, while this pilot course serves as a starting point in terms of introducing OS to PhD candidates in a cross-domain, updated content-based based, there are still some areas for improvement, especially in terms of FAIR-by-design compliance (e.g. micro-credentials and badges). Moreover, despite the positive results on the evaluation and impact of the course on students, there is a lack of a feedback questionnaire for students after the course that provides quantitative feedback.

These areas will be improved and further developed in later training. The content of this pilot will also be discussed and co-create during the TtT course on *“Shaping Open Science Champions: a train-the-trainers course for educators of PhD candidates”* to be held in May 2025.

Appendix

Below we summarise in a table the alignment of the pilot’s program, learning objectives and activities with the corresponding MVS profile’s skills and competences (MVS profile for Early Career Researcher) and the FAIR-by-design methodology:

<i>UC3M Ticket2OS course</i>		<i>MVS ECR profile</i>	<i>FAIR-by-design methodology: Bloom's taxonomy verbs</i>		
	Proposed Modules	Topics	Skills and competences	Module learning objectives	Assignment
1	Ethos and Introduction to Open Science	Introduction about the course. Learning outcomes and evaluation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Good understanding of OS and its practices, in a discipline-specific context, particularly knowledgeable of policies, opportunities and practices of OS (e.g., open access, data storage and archival). 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Develop a thorough understanding of Open Science principles, practices, initiatives, policies, resources and challenges, within a discipline-specific context. -Advocate for the adoption of Open Science and FAIR principles, contributing to the wider uptake of skills and organizational capacities. 	Assignment /practice 1: a) Discussion: Let's play True or False: Open Science misconceptions and b) Complete the Survey: What do you want to know about Open Science?
		You & Open Science: a new paradigm for your research (icebreaking)			
What is Open Science (Open Science, Open Knowledge, Open Research, Open Scholarship)					
Why Open Science and How to Make It Happen. Benefits of Open Science for researchers and society.					
Open Science Components and Challenges					
Current Researchers 35 times Open: The European Competence Framework for Researchers (CFR. 2022)					
Evolution and current policies for Open Science (declarations, initiatives and the rules of the game): - Main actions, documents and policies in Europe and worldwide (UNESCO Recommendation) to promote and implement Open Science. - Open Science in the Spanish Research Landscape (Spanish Legislation on Science and Universities, Doctoral rules and practices RD 99/2011, Spanish Strategy on Open Science (ENCA2023).					
2	Planning your responsible research in the Open	How to become an Open Responsible Scientist	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Sound knowledge of the data life cycle and adequate capacity to implement discipline-specific FAIR principles - Ability to assess FAIRness of existing resources and make OS-compliant choices to capture, process, analyse, and preserve data - Upgradable digital skills: experience in using tools for conducting research, managing and sharing research output. Commitment to undertaking training on digital-oriented research practices - Good understanding of ethical principles 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Gain expertise in the data life cycle field and implement discipline-specific FAIR principles effectively. -Assess and enhance the FAIRness of existing resources, making informed choices in capturing, processing, analyzing, and preserving data. 	Assignment /practice 2: Building up the ECR-PhD UC3M Open Science Community. Register to the Community Slack channel + OS UC3M listserv and start you interaction.
		Including Open Science Practices in the whole research Cycle.			
		Open Science Tools and collaborative research. (101Tools-Utrecht and DOST (Digital Open Science Tools): Reference management and discovery tools; Tools for analysis; Collaborative writing platforms; other tools to produce content; Annotation and review tools; Tools for your research outreach.			
		Planning YOUR STRATEGY to Open Science: You, Your thesis, Your publications, Your data (sharing), your other research outcomes			
		EDI: Equity, Diversity and Inclusion principles and standards			
		Initiatives and resources for Early Career Researchers and PhD candidates to practice Open Science			
3	Disseminating your research: Open access publications	What is open access publishing?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Good understanding of OS and its practices, in a discipline-specific context, particularly knowledgeable of policies, opportunities and practices of OS (e.g., open access, data storage and archival). - Upgradable digital skills: experience in using tools for conducting research, managing and sharing 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - provide a comprehensive understanding of open access publishing and routes; strategies to enhance their research visibility; new metrics, trends, agreements and impact factors on publishing; and 	Assignment / practice 3: a) Plan the OA of all your publications: Chose the right OA route for your publications: Self-archive one of your current publications being aware of the policies in
		OA history and declarations: +20 years of OA			
		Benefits and challenges of OA publishing.			
		Open Access routes: gold, green, diamond, etc.			
		PlanS & cOAlitionS, transformative agreements and current trends (Rights Retention Strategy (RRS).			
		Versions of your paper: version of the author (preprint/postprint), VoR, etc. and how to know the right version to share (Sherpa/Romeo)			
		Preprints and Open Peer Review			
Repositories: types and use.					

Pilot OS Essentials for PhD students - UC3M Ticket to Open Science

		<p>Social networks for scientists. Repositories vs. Social Scientific Networks (ex. ResearchGate)</p> <p>Predatory publishers/journals: How to identify them</p> <p>How to choose an Open Science Journal? criteria, resources and practical guidance</p>	<p>research output. Commitment to undertaking training on digital-oriented research practices</p>	<p>cultivation of a professional digital identity in the academic context.</p>	<p>Sherpa/Romeo, or local websites (e. g. Dulcinea in Spain). b) Students should watch: https://paywallthemovie.com.</p>
4	Disseminating your research data: Open and FAIR data	<p>What is Open Data, Open Research Data and FAIR data.</p> <p>Types of row data (qualitative and quantitative).</p> <p>FAIR data principles: Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Reusable.</p> <p>CARE principles (Collective benefit, Authority to Control, Responsibility and Ethics).</p> <p>Metadata and PIDs.</p> <p>Data Management Plans (DMP) and outcome management plans.</p> <p>How to create a DMP: Tools and standards.</p> <p>Regulation around data/open data, further than research data: GDPR, EU directive on Open Data (1024/2019)</p> <p>The principle "as open as possible, as closed as necessary"</p> <p>Licensing FAIR data for Reuse (see. ELSI session)</p> <p>Current Data repositories and EOSC. Search for RD repositories (re3data). Tools (OSF), and other infrastructures.</p>	<p>- Good understanding of OS and its practices, in a discipline-specific context, particularly knowledgeable of policies, opportunities and practices of OS (e.g., open access, data storage and archival).</p> <p>- Ability to assess FAIRness of existing resources and make OS-compliant choices to capture, process, analyse, and preserve data</p> <p>- Research management skills: Ability to design an open research strategy, implement an open research vision, and coordinate research activities that embed open science principle</p> <p>- Demonstrate knowledge about the data planning requirement of different research funders.</p> <p>- Sound knowledge of the data life cycle and adequate capacity to implement discipline-specific FAIR principles</p>	<p>- discern the different types of row data and the differences between Open Data, Open Research Data and FAIR data; explore the Fair data and the CARE principles; understand the parts, steps and tools of a DMP; get familiar with the main data regulations and repositories; and learn how to license your data</p>	<p>Assignment / practice 4: Plan the openness and FAIRness of your data: Make a DMP for your thesis. You can use any of the tools provided in this session. You might create your DMP during the whole course, upload it in AG or share it openly available as part of the content of your final post in the course Blog.</p>
5	How UC3M will help you to be an Open Scientist: UniOS & Library support	<p>Authorship and affiliation</p> <p>Persistent Identifier for researchers: ORCID uses at UC3M</p> <p>Your thesis step by step: a library guide to help you with your thesis</p> <p>How to publish in Open Access your thesis and your publications:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The Institutional Repository e-Archivo. - Your thesis in Open Access (embargoes and exceptions) <p>Open Science and the dissemination of research outcomes. Regional Research Portal: InvestigaM (Consorcio Madroño):</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - How to create a data management plan for your thesis - Regional Repository: e-Ciencia - Data Management and Regional Data Repository: e-CienciaDatos: a place for your thesis's data <p>Blog I+B: Investigación y Biblioteca (R+L: Research and Library)</p> <p>Where we are and how to make it happen:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Open Science support (UniOS) - Full Open Science Pilot (FOS). 	<p>- Good understanding of OS and its practices, in a discipline-specific context, particularly knowledgeable of policies, opportunities and practices of OS (e.g., open access, data storage and archival).</p> <p>- Research management skills: Ability to design an open research strategy, implement an open research vision, and coordinate research activities that embed open science principle</p> <p>- Entrepreneurial skills: Ability to identify and apply for OS funding opportunities; ability to acquire funding that furthers open science goals, writing grants and funding applications</p>	<p>- Explore what your institution can make for you, your publications and research dissemination (library services, guides, repositories, etc.) and how to extend your research beyond academia (open innovation and entrepreneurship)</p>	<p>Assignment / practice 5: The students will learn how the uc3m's infrastructures will help them in different phases of their thesis, and also how to finally publish their thesis (e-Archivo) and their data (e-CienciaDatos).</p>
6	Pre-registration and Reproducibility	<p>Reusability, Replication, and Reproducibility (RRR):</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The role of reproducibility in Scientific research. - Reproducibility crisis and National Reproducibility Networks. - Challenges in reproducibility: publication bias, QRP (Questionable Research, Practices, etc.) - Strategies and best practices on improving reproducibility. - Create a reproducible data analysis using knitr. - Tools for improving reproducibility: RMarkdown, Jupyter notebook, etc. <p>Concept of preregistration and disciplines that practice pre-registration:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Design a pre-registered study. - Pre-registration platforms and templates: Aspredicted, OSF, etc. 	<p>- Disseminate knowledge, the reproducibility of scientific findings and facilitating the sharing of research inputs and outputs.</p> <p>- Upgradable digital skills: experience in using tools for conducting research, managing and sharing research output. Commitment to undertaking training on digital-oriented research practices</p>	<p>- Improving the dissemination of research outputs, understanding the importance of reproducibility, its challenges and the main tools and resources to make it happen; take the first steps in the preregistration process, from its plan design to relevant tools and templates</p>	<p>Assignment / practice 6: a) Hands-on exercise in data management and analyses for successful reproducible research. b) Hands-on pre-registration or registration of an individual research.</p>

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7	Ethical, Legal and Social Issues (ELSI) of Open Science	<p>Legal issues in research outputs:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Intellectual Property Rights, the Data and Digital Legislation and Open Science - Intellectual property rights, copyright and its exceptions - Open licensing, license compatibility and academic freedom - Choosing a license for your Research Objects: publications, software, data. - Rights Retention Strategy, Secondary publication rights - An overview of the Data and Digital Legislation from the researcher's perspective - Opportunities and challenges for data access and (re)use in the Data and Digital Legislation. - Privacy and Personal Data Protection and regulations. Principles, roles and responsibilities in Personal Data Processing - Interoperability and shareability of personal data and risks - Anonymization and Data Protection Impact Assessment (DPIA) - Balancing Data Protection and OS/FAIR Principles <p>Ethics in Open Science:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - General Ethical Principles, Frameworks (e.g. RRI: Responsible Research and Innovation) and Codes (e.g. the European Code of Conduct for Research Integrity) applicable to Research in the EU - Best practices in Open Research 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Good understanding of the relevant legal aspects related to research and their field of expertise, and relevant Open Science practices, including, but not limited to: Intellectual Property Rights (eg copyright, patents, and trade secrets) and other Non-Personal Data (eg use of IoT data and research data), Personal Data Protection and Governance (eg processing Personal Data under the current legal framework, and following existing policies on Data Protection), Privacy, and (Open) Licensing rules and frameworks. - Ability to balance (personal and non-personal) data protection requirements with Open Science/FAIR principles. - Good understanding of ethical principles (e.g., transparency, diversity, and accountability) and best practices (e.g., avoiding bias in data processing when using data-driven technologies) applicable to their field of expertise, including, but not limited to the general ethical principles, frameworks and codes of conduct applicable to research (e.g., the RRI Framework; the European Code of Conduct for Research Integrity); 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Introducing relevant legal aspects and regulations related to research (IPR, Copyright, Rights Retention Strategy, DPIA, interoperability and shareability, etc.); provide a comprehensive understanding about types of licensing, how to choose a license and how to balance Data Protection and OS/FAIR principles 	<p>Assignment / practice 7: a) Each student will choose licenses for their current or pretending Research Objects (RO). b) Play Dilemma Game (online/app): The Dilemma Game confronts researchers with difficult dilemmas in the context of a critical dialogue, supporting them in further developing their own 'moral compass'.</p>
8	Citizen Science and public engagement	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> What is citizen science. History and evolution of CS. Citizen Science and public engagement: difference and confluence. Citizen science principles (10) and characteristics. Types of citizen science projects. CS platforms and communities (CitizenScience toolkit, SciStarter, national CS platforms and communities). Create your own project of CS. CS in educational settings: Open Educational Resources and citizen science Other approaches to citizen science: CERI (Community Engagement Responsible Research and Innovation), YUFE approach to CS within YUFERING project. <p>Citizen Science successful use cases at UC3M:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - LADA-UC3M: citizen science in urban archaeology research. - Mental Health research and citizen science. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Research management skills: Ability to design an open research strategy, implement an open research vision, and coordinate research activities that embed open science principles - Upgradable digital skills: experience in using tools for conducting research, managing and sharing research output. Commitment to undertaking training on digital-oriented research practices 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Provide a comprehensive understanding of citizen science, including its history, principles, and various project types; differentiate citizen science from public engagement, explore key platforms and communities, and develop their own projects using best practices; examine how citizen science integrates into education and research through Open Educational Resources (OER), alternative approaches (CERI framework and YUFE initiatives) and case studies at UC3M. 	<p>Assignment / practice 8: a) Quiz about what is and what is not citizen science. b) Each student should find and analyze a CS project of his/her discipline and/or related with her/his dissertation.</p>
9	RRA Responsible Research Assessment: Towards a reform of the Research Evaluation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Traditional Research Assessment methods and practices: the biggest barrier for Open Science. Principles of Responsible Research Assessment (RRA). Benefits of Implementing RRA in Research Evaluation. Challenges to Reforming Research Assessment. Current movements and initiatives to Reform Research Assessment world-wide: DORA Declaration, Leiden Manifesto, The Metric Tide, CoARA, etc. CoARA: an opportunity to change research evaluation. CoARA Working Groups and National Chapters. Case Studies of Successful Implementation of RRA. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Good understanding of ethical principles (e.g., transparency, diversity, and accountability) and best practices (e.g., avoiding bias in data processing when using data-driven technologies) applicable to their field of expertise, including, but not limited to the general ethical principles, frameworks and codes of conduct applicable to research (e.g., the RRI Framework; the European Code of Conduct for Research 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Introduce principles and benefits of Responsible Research Assessment (RRA) and the challenges posed by traditional research assessment methods and the reforming research assessment; examine global initiatives such as the DORA Declaration, Leiden Manifesto, The Metric Tide, and CoARA; 	<p>Assignment / practice 9: a) Create your narrative CV and upload it in AG assignment. You might include it as part of your final open post in the course Blog.</p>

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		<p>Tools and Resources for Implementing RRA: Next Generation Metrics and CAM (Career Assessment Matrix). Open bibliographic data (open metadata).</p>	<p>Integrity);</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Upgradable digital skills: experience in using tools for conducting research, managing and sharing research output. Commitment to undertaking training on digital-oriented research practices - Ability to assess FAIRness of existing resources and make OS-compliant choices to capture, process, analyse, and preserve data 	<p>analyze successful case studies of RRA implementation and explore tools like Next Generation Metrics and the Career Assessment Matrix (CAM) to enhance research evaluation; highlight the importance of open bibliographic data and the role of early- and mid-career researchers (EMCR) in driving assessment reforms.</p>	
10	<p>Discipline-oriented Open Science</p>	<p>Doctoral candidates will make groups by discipline/area (e. g. Social Sciences, Humanities, Engineering, Law, etc.) and contact the University Unit on Open Science (UniOS) to have a special session focusing on the OS issues in their discipline. To organize yourselves by groups, you might use the Forum in AG or contact students from the same discipline/same interests through the Slack Community Channel.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Good understanding of OS and its practices, in a discipline-specific context, particularly knowledgeable of policies, opportunities and practices of OS (e.g., open access, data storage and archival). 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Collaborate with peers in their discipline to explore Open Science (OS) issues specific to their research field; engage with the University Unit on Open Science (UniOS) to gain insights into discipline-specific OS practices and policies; identify key Open Science challenges and opportunities relevant to their research area; develop strategies for implementing Open Science principles in their field through group discussions and expert consultations. 	<p>Book an appointment!!</p>